

FINDING CRITICAL USER IN SOCIAL COMMUNITIES VIA GRAPH CONVOLUTION

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ABSTRACT

Finding critical users whose existence keeps a social community cohesive and large is an important issue in social networks. In the literature, such criticalness of a user is measured by the number of followers who will leave the community together when the user leaves. By taking a social community as a k -core, which can be computed in linear time, the problem of finding critical users is to find a set of nodes, U , with a user-given size b in a k -core community that maximizes the number of nodes (followers) to be deleted from the k -core when all nodes in U are deleted. This problem is known to be NP-hard. In the literature, the state-of-the-art approach, a greedy algorithm is proposed with no guarantee on the set of nodes U found, since there does not exist a submodular function the greedy algorithm can use to get a better answer iteratively. Furthermore, the greedy algorithm designed is to handle k -core in any social networks such that it does not consider the structural complexity of a given single graph and cannot get the global optimal by the local optimal found in iterations. In this paper, we propose a novel learning-based approach. Distinguished from traditional experience-based heuristics, we propose a neural network model, called Self-attentive Core Graph Convolution Network (*SCGCN*), to capture the hidden structure of the criticalness among node combinations that

break the engagement of a specific social community. Supervised by sampling node combinations, *SCGCN* has the ability to inference the criticalness of unseen combinations of nodes. To further reduce the sampling and inference space, we propose a deterministic strategy to prune unpromising nodes on the graph. Our experiments conducted on many real-world graphs show that *SCGCN* significantly improves the quality of the solution compared with the state-of-the-art greedy algorithm.

INTRODUCTION

Exploring the critical entities in networks has attracted interests in recent years [1], [2], [3], [4], as motivated by the fact that there is a need to understand who plays an important role in a large dense subgraph with possibly thousands of nodes found for analytical tasks in social networks (e.g., biological networks, etc). This task is beneficial to many consequent mining tasks such as recommendation and influence maximization. For instance, in social network analysis, it is vital to identify the opinion leaders from existing communities. To evaluate the criticalness of a user set, U , in a community, recent approaches model it by the number of followers, where the followers of U are the users who will take the same action to leave the community when the users in U leave. It is worth mentioning that a follower of U may not directly connect to any user in U and can be an indirect follower following some connections to a user in U . The problem of

finding critical users over a social community is to identify U such that the largest number of nodes (followers) will be deleted from the social community when U are deleted. Zhang et al. studied critical user detection as a collapsed k -core problem [1]. In brief, it considers a social community as a k -core for a given k and finds a set of nodes, U , with a given size b , that will trigger the max number of nodes to be deleted from the k -core, if all nodes in U are deleted. As shown in [1], the collapsed k -core problem is non-trivial and is proven to be NP-hard. In the scope of this paper, the problem of critical user detection is equivalent to the collapsed k -core problem. And we use critical user detection in the following definition as we concentrate on finding the node set U . To find such U , Zhang et al. in [1] proposed a greedy algorithm which is the state-of-the-art. We explain the greedy algorithm in brief. Let $f(u)$ be a function, for every node u in a k -core community, as the number of nodes to be deleted from the k -core community when the node u is deleted. The greedy algorithm will repeatedly select the node u with the largest $f(u)$ value to be added into U until $|U| = b$. The greedy algorithm performs well in practice. But, as $f(u)$ has been proven to be non-submodular, there is no error bound for the greedy algorithm to find such a set of U for any social communities. We show the drawback of the greedy algorithm using an example.

LITERATURE REVIEW

IN “ESCUDERO-GARZS, J.J., BOUSOO-CALZN, C.: ‘AN ANALYSIS OF THE NETWORK SELECTION PROBLEM FOR HETEROGENEOUS ENVIRONMENTS WITH USER-OPERATOR JOINT SATISFACTION AND MULTI-RAT TRANSMISSION’, WIRELESS COMMUNICATIONS AND MOBILE COMPUTING’ (HINDAWI PUBLICATIONS, UK., 2017)” The trend in wireless networks is

that several wireless radio access technologies (RATs) coexist in the same area, forming heterogeneous networks in which the users may connect to any of the available RATs. The problem of associating a user to the most suitable RAT, known as network selection problem (NSP), is of capital importance for the satisfaction of the users in these emerging environments. However, also the satisfaction of the operator is important in this scenario. In this work, we propose that a connection may be served by more than one RAT by using multi-RAT terminals. We formulate the NSP with multiple RAT association based on utility functions that take into consideration both user’s satisfaction and provider’s satisfaction. As users are characterized according to their expected quality of service, our results exhaustively analyze the influence of the user’s profile, along with the network topology and the type of applications served. In the realm of wireless communications, a user has nowadays different possibilities of connectivity: 3G, 4G, WiFi, and WiMAX, among others. Very often, the access points (APs) or base stations (BSs) that provide these radio access technologies (RATs) coexist in the same location and, consequently, their connectivity services overlap. This scenario is known as *heterogeneous network* (HetNet) and has received an increasing attention in the past years [1,2]. On the other hand, user’s satisfaction perceived when he/she is using any application is directly related to the quality of service (QoS), which is consequently a decisive factor for successful network exploitation [3–5]. Within this paradigm, we are interested in the network (or RAT) selection problem (NSP) with QoS, in which each terminal (user) is assigned to the most

suitable available network complying with the QoS requirements.

IN “ZHANG, C., ZHAO, H., DENG, S.: ‘A DENSITY-BASED OFFLOADING STRATEGY FOR IOT DEVICES IN EDGE COMPUTING SYSTEMS’, *IEEE ACCESS*, 2018, 6, PP. 73520–73530”

Collaboration spaces formed from edge servers can efficiently improve the quality of experience of service subscribers. In this paper, we first utilize a strategy based on the density of Internet of Things (IoT) devices and k -means algorithm to partition network of edge servers, then an algorithm for IoT devices' computation offloading decisions is proposed, i.e., whether we need to offload IoT devices' workload to edge servers, and which edge server to choose if migration is needed. The combination of locations of edge servers and the geographic distribution of various IoT devices can significantly improve the scheduling of network resources and satisfy requirements of service subscribers. We analyze and build mathematical models about whether/how to offload tasks from various IoT devices to edge servers. In order to better simulate operations of the mobile edge servers in more realistic scenarios, the input size of each IoT device is uncertain and regarded as a random variable following some probability distribution based on long-term

observations. On the basis of that, an algorithm utilizing sample average approximation method is proposed to discuss whether the tasks to be executed locally or offloaded. Besides, the algorithm proposed can also help decide whether service relocation/migration is needed or not.

IN “ANPALAGAN, A., AWAIS, M., AHMED, A., *ET AL.*: ‘RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN MULTICLOUD IOT RADIO ACCESS NETWORK’, *IEEE INTERNET THINGS J.*, 2019, 6, (2), PP. 3014–3023”

—Cloud radio access network (CRAN) is a promising approach to provide ubiquitous and on demand access to future Internet of Things (IoT) networks. The existing CRANs assume a single cloud which suffers from computational complexity and signaling latency to support massive number of IoT devices in large scale network deployments. This work focuses on the scheduling of IoT devices in a multicloud IoT network scenario. The work considers the downlink of an IoT network consisting of multiple clouds, each coordinates a cluster of several base stations (BSs) allowing joint signal processing. The transmit frame of each BS is composed of several resource blocks (RBs). The multiple clouds are linked to the central cloud which performs scheduling of IoT devices and

synchronization of transmit frames. The work models the IoT devices to RBs assignment problem considering the inter-cloud and intra-cloud interference. The optimization problem maximizes the overall network utilization under practical network constraints. Further, this work also proposes a low complexity heuristic algorithm to solve the constraint resource allocation problem in linear time. Complexity analysis of proposed algorithm is carried out and simulation results for a number of IoT network scenarios demonstrate that proposed solution is numerically accurate and performs close to the optimal solution. Internet of Things (IoT) refers to a set of smart, uniquely identifiable computing devices connected to the Internet. The massive deployment of IoT devices causes several challenges including increased volume, high data rates, spectrum scarcity, energy efficiency and strict latency requirements. Integration of IoT systems in existing and 5G networks is the key to address these challenges. A combination of 5G and industrial IoT (IIoT) is now becoming an emerging paradigm for connectivity and data transfer. Applications of 5G assisted IIoT includes, but not limited to, wireless sensor networks (WSN) [1], [2], concurrent data collections [3], device-to-device and data aggregation [4], monitoring solution for advanced

predictive maintenance applications [5], cyber-physical systems [6], energy management [7], machine-to-machine communications [8], ecosystem [9], agriculture [10], smart cities [11], healthcare [12] and video streaming [13] etc IN **“ROY, A., CHAPORKAR, P., KARANDIKAR, A.: ‘OPTIMAL RADIO ACCESS TECHNOLOGY SELECTION ALGORITHM FOR LTE-WIFI NETWORK’, *IEEE TRANS. VEH. TECHNOL.*, 2018, 67, (7), PP. 6446–6460”** Heterogeneous Network (HetNet) comprises of multiple Radio Access Technologies (RATs) allowing a user to associate with a specific RAT and steer to other RATs in a seamless manner. To cope up with the unprecedented growth of data traffic, mobile data can be offloaded to Wireless Fidelity (WiFi) in a Long Term Evolution (LTE) based HetNet. In this paper, an optimal RAT selection problem is considered to maximize the total system throughput in an LTE-WiFi system with offload capability. Another formulation is also developed where maximizing the total system throughput is subject to a constraint on the voice user blocking probability. It is proved that the optimal policies for the association and offloading of voice/data users contain threshold structures. As a policy search over the entire policy space may become computationally inefficient,

we propose computationally efficient algorithms based on the threshold structures for the association and offloading of users in LTE-WiFi HetNet. Simulation results are presented to demonstrate the voice user blocking probability and the total system throughput performance of the proposed algorithms in comparison to other benchmark algorithms. To meet the ever-increasing Quality of Service (QoS) requirements of users, various Radio Access Technologies (RATs) have been standardized [1]-[2]. Each RAT has different characteristics regarding associated parameters like coverage and capacity. It has been predicted that by 2021 monthly global mobile data traffic will exceed 49 exabytes [3]. This unprecedented growth in data traffic has become one of the serious challenges for cellular network operators. To address this issue, both from users' and network providers' point of view, it has become necessary that different RATs interwork with each other. IN **“VENKATARAMAN, H., KALYAMPUDI, P., MUNTEAN, G.M.: ‘CASHEW: CLUSTER-BASED ADAPTIVE SCHEME FOR MULTIMEDIA DELIVERY IN HETEROGENEOUS WIRELESS NETWORKS’, *SPRINGER WIREL. PERSONAL COMMUN.*, 2012, 62, (3), PP. 517–536”** The wireless industry has evolved rapidly over the last decade or so. The wireless technology has evolved from simple voice

services to text-based messages such as email and web traffic, and then towards multimedia applications like Internet phone, video conferencing and video on demand (VoD). The user today not only wants to stay connected at any place and at any point of time, but also wants high quality information and entertainment programs at a very affordable cost. The next generation wireless networks strives to achieve these requirements and in the process, has brought many significant changes in data networking; including an all-IP based wireless network [1]. Therefore, in order to support video transmission over a wide coverage area, a fundamental change in the wireless architecture is required. A ubiquitous wireless multimedia transmission calls for communication across a heterogeneous wireless network which in-turn demands multihop communication between the source and the destination node. The multimedia transmission between different wireless devices would be established over a multihop heterogeneous wireless network (WiFi, WLAN, WiMAX, WAN, MAN, etc) using a novel proxy-client-server model. However, multihop design causes an increase in the overhead signals, and significantly, results in an increase in time delay in the network [2]. In addition, real-time delivery of information is extremely time-sensitive and does not allow delay and jitter in the incoming signals. Given these technological bottlenecks, inspite of being extensively researched over the last decade, peer-to-peer distributed multihop transmission for multimedia delivery would probably take

few more years to come up as a practical solution [3].

EXISTING SYSTEM: Network selection in wireless networks plays a crucial role in ensuring efficient resource utilization, optimal performance, and user satisfaction. Existing network selection approaches primarily fall into two categories: device-centric and network-centric approaches. Device-centric approaches prioritize the preferences and requirements of individual devices, considering factors such as device capabilities, application requirements, and user preferences. These approaches aim to select the network that best suits the device's specific needs, such as signal strength-based selection for optimal signal reception, application-aware selection for specific application requirements, and user-preference-based selection for user-defined network priorities. Network-centric approaches, on the other hand, focus on optimizing network resource utilization and minimizing congestion by considering factors such as network load, interference levels, and channel availability. These approaches aim to select the network that can best accommodate the device's traffic without overloading the network, such as load balancing for distributing traffic across networks, interference avoidance for minimizing interference impact, and channel availability for ensuring channel access. While both device-centric and

network-centric approaches have their advantages, they also face limitations. Device-centric approaches may not adequately consider network constraints, potentially leading to congestion or suboptimal network performance. Network-centric approaches may overlook user preferences, potentially resulting in user dissatisfaction. Additionally, existing network selection approaches often lack real-time adaptation to dynamic network conditions and seamless integration with existing network architectures. Therefore, there is a need for a more comprehensive and balanced network selection approach that considers both device preferences and network resource availability in a real-time manner. The "Dual Priority: A Real-Time and Integrated, Device-and-Network-Centric Wireless Network Selection" scheme addresses these limitations by combining device preferences with network resource availability in a balanced and adaptive framework to optimize network selection decisions for both individual users and network operators.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

This work proposes an integrated hybrid architecture for real-time network selection. Fig. 2 shows the block diagram of the 'dual priority' architecture. It has two distinct components: DE-SMART architecture and

MCS-NS. The proposed solution considers the objective of both device-side and network-side. Hence, the technique has two sub-modules: a client-side technique called DESMART and the network-side technique called MCS-NS, which takes inputs from a device. DE-SMART has multiple steps, as can be seen later. However, an important point to be noted is that DESMART is independent of the network-centric solution. Further, the process of MCS-NS is independent of DE-SMART though the values of DE-SMART determine the clustering techniques in MCS-NS. Given that MCS-NS has been developed such that it functions based on the inputs received from DE-SMART, the output of MCS-NS will provide priority to both device-based and network-based preferences. Fig. 3 shows the block diagram of the device-side architecture – DE-SMART. DE-SMART runs on the subscriber's handset. It identifies the different available networks as seen by the device; and then ranks these networks. The ranking is done based on different factors such as user mobility, user preferences, application requirements, signal strength, network conditions and energy consumption of the mobile device. The main idea of ranking is to ensure that QoS is maintained for the subscribers. The first step in DE-SMART is collecting information about all available networks.

As can be seen in Fig. 3, apart from data collection, DE-SMART has three more steps.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

The expanding use of data for various services like high rate services such as multimedia, social networking, etc. has put enormous pressure on the network operators to use a heterogeneous wireless environment. In such a scenario, the seamless movement of the subscribers between different cellular and between cellular and Wi-Fi networks would reduce traffic congestion and provide improvement in the QoS. The dual priority scheme proposed in this paper investigates the use of both device and the network to rank the available networks and select the best possible network for offloading each subscriber. It has been found that such a mechanism results in an extremely less time requirement, up-to three times less, as compared to other network-centric techniques. Importantly, the dual priority scheme provides the much-needed flexibility in taking into account the device's preferences and also providing the best available network, based on the network operator's perspective.

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